

EVALUATION PLAN

D5.1

Fig. 01

Project:	PIE News – Poverty, Income, and Employment News (H2020-ICT-2015)
Duration:	1st July 2016 – 30th June 2019 (36 months)
Contract number:	Grant Agreement Number 687922
Partners:	University of Trento, Basic Income Network Italy, Centre for Peace Studies, Stichting STAFF, CREATE-NET, Stichting Dyne.org, Abertay University, Madeira Interactive Technologies Institute
Document Number:	D5.1
Contractual Date:	30/11/2016
Workpackage:	WP5
Distribution / Types:	PU
Version:	Final
Total Number of Pages:	29
File:	PIE-D5.1
Authors:	Francesco Botto

The PIE News project involves pilot users and stakeholders in the design and use of a Community Awareness Platform for the needs of new poor and of people in precarious working conditions. Design and implementation practices have been structured in close relation with the project evaluation task. PIE News evaluation leverages on the participation of project partners in both the preparation and execution of evaluation activities. It aims to monitor on-line and off-line project activities performed with and by users and stakeholders, with the final objective to improve the project activities and technologies and to disseminate projects results in a continuous process M1-M36. This document describes the detailed project evaluation plan. It focuses in particular on project design workshops' evaluation-related activities, but includes other aspects of the project. Given the participatory and incremental character of both project and evaluation activities, the plan is subject to further changes.

European Commission

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 687922

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fig. 02

This document presents the detailed evaluation plan for the PIE News project as an evolution of the early plan after the negotiation and agreement on the evaluation tasks with the project partners during the first five months of the project. The plan is defined with four characteristics: it is incremental and integrated, meaning that it will be gradually developed and refined over time with some tasks that will leverage upon project activities (e.g.: design); and it is participatory and sustainable, in the sense that project partners are asked to co-design the evaluation activities in a comfortable way for everyone. The rules of the participative approach have been validated by the consortium and some evaluation activities that were not considered by the early plan have been executed (Early User Survey) or pre-planned (User Registration Survey, User Stakeholders Satisfaction Survey).

The project evaluation comprises both on-line and off-line evaluation tasks. For example, web and social networks analysis (through Logs and Web analytics) and Network Dynamics Analysis will be used for the monitoring of web tools and the improvement of on-line networks. Evaluation of other project activities that require the collaboration of project partners, (potential and actual) platform users and local stakeholders – especially in the local Pilots – require off-line evaluation processes.

Project evaluation activities will be continuous during the 36 months, with centralized management and the

online involvement of partners. Project workshops (DWS) constitute the core place for the consortium discussion, agreement, validation and – in some cases – execution of evaluation tasks.

This plan and the Early User Survey have been validated during DWS1. The other evaluation tasks will leverage on consortium activities during the workshops: User Registration Survey, self-evaluation of pilots' activities, planning MockUps' user feedback activities, pilots' evaluation of MockUps and platform releases at the pilot level, and planning of the final evaluation.

Other evaluation tasks are expected to be completed mainly outside of workshops: feedback with satisfaction metrics and comments from users and stakeholders after every activity – involving external people – at the pilot level; platform users' participation monitoring, website and project social channels participation monitoring; networks dynamics monitoring; useful deliverables, reports and more or less formal guidelines for PIE News improvements; and some selected evaluation results published online through the "evaluation dashboard".

The intermediate and final evaluation of the many dimensions that comprise the project will leverage on the Self-Assessment Toolkit (SAT) for assessing the multidimensional impacts of the project offered by the IA4SI project.

DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY

DATE	VERSION	AUTHOR	SUMMARY OF CHANGES
19/10/2016	0.1	Francesco Botto	Table of Contents approved by Chiara Bassetti and Maurizio Teli
14/11/2016	1.0	Francesco Botto	First version ready for internal review
18/11/2016	2.0	Francesco Botto	Second version after internal review process
22/11/2016	3.0	Francesco Botto	Third version after the final internal check
30/11/2016	Final	Francesco Botto	Final version with the official template

CONTRIBUTORS

FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ORGANIZATION	CONTRIBUTION
Francesco	Botto	CREATE-NET	Author
Chiara	Bassetti	UNITN	TOC proposal review
Maurizio	Teli	MITI	TOC proposal review
Matteo	Moretti	UNITN	Elements of section 2.2.5
Stefania	Ottaviano	CREATE-NET	Elements of section 4.2
Anna	Wilson	AU	V1 internal review
Mariacristina	Sciannamblo	MITI	V1 internal review
Daniela	Paes Leão	MDC	Adoption of official template with VIGs

ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
DWS	Workshop (the “Design Workshop” in the project framework)
KPI	Key Process Indicator
WP	Work Package
KOM	Kick Off Meeting
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
PC	Project Coordinator
PL	Project Leader
RIC	Research and Innovator Coordinator
EUS	Early Users’ Survey
USSS	Users Stakeholders Satisfaction Survey
URS	Users’ Registration Survey
NDA	Network Dynamics Analysis
CN	CREATE-NET
MS	Milestone
SW	Software
TOC	Table of contents
VIGs	Visual Identity Guidelines

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Evaluation Plan	1
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	3
CONTRIBUTORS	4
ACRONYMS	5
TABLE OF CONTENTS	6
LIST OF FIGURES	8
LIST OF TABLES	9
1. INTRODUCTION	10
2. FROM THE EARLY PLANNING TO A PRACTICAL APPROACH	12
2.1 EARLY PLANNING FROM THE PROJECT PROPOSAL	12
2.1.1 Main evaluation components and tools	12
2.1.2 Early workshops plan	13
2.1.3 Main deadlines	13
2.1.4 Key Process Indicators	13
2.1.5 Risk detection evaluation-related issues	13
2.2 PRACTICAL APPROACH TO EVALUATION	14
2.2.1 Incremental & integrated	14
2.2.2 Participative & sustainable	14
2.2.3 Consortium agreement on the participative approach	14
2.2.4 Starting with the unplanned Early User Survey (EUS)	14
2.2.5 Visual dissemination of evaluation results	15
3. WORKSHOP-RELATED EVALUATION ACTIVITIES	16
3.1 INTRODUCTION	16
3.2 PARTNERS' AGREEMENT ON EVALUATION-RELATED ACTIVITIES AT DWSS	17
3.2.1 DWS1 – M3: September 2016	17
3.2.2 DWS2 – M7: January 2017	17
3.2.3 DWS3 – M13: July 2017	18
3.2.4 DWS4 – M21: March 2018	19
4. FOCUS ON SOME SPECIFIC EVALUATION ACTIVITIES	20
4.1 USER-STAKEHOLDER SATISFACTION SURVEY (USSS)	20

4.1.1 Introduction and aim	20
4.1.2 Strategy	20
4.2 NETWORK DYNAMICS ANALYSIS (NDA)	21
4.3 GOOGLE ANALYTICS, FACEBOOK INSIGHTS AND HASHTAG ANALYTICS	21
4.4 INTERMEDIATE AND FINAL SELF-ASSESSMENT	21
5. AN EXAMPLE: THE EARLY USER SURVEY PREPARATION	23
5.1 OBJECTIVES, STRUCTURE AND STRATEGY	23
5.2 PARTICIPATORY PROCESS	24
5.3 THE ENGLISH QUESTIONNAIRE	24
5.3.1 Introduction	24
5.3.2 User consent	24
5.3.3 Questionnaire	24
5.3.4 End message	25
5.4 LINKS FOR THE COMPARISON OF RESULTS	26
5.5 PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA	26
6. CONCLUSION: OPEN ISSUES	27
REFERENCES	28
ANNEXES	29

LIST OF FIGURES

FIGURE	TITLE	PAGE
01	Zagreb Workshop	01
02	Zagreb Workshop	02
03	Zagreb Workshop	10
04	A timeline vision of PIE News evaluation activities.	10
05	Zagreb Workshop	12
06	Design workshops-related evaluation activities' early planning.	12
07	The incremental character of PIE News evaluation planning.	14
08	The integrated character of PIE News evaluation activities.	14
09	Zagreb Workshop	14
10	Example of radar chart for the PIE News evaluation dashboard.	15
11	Example of stacked bar chart for the PIE News evaluation dashboard.	15
12	Zagreb Workshop	16
13	The evaluation activities leveraging on PIE News design workshops.	16
14	Zagreb Workshop	17
15	Zagreb Workshop	20
16	Zagreb Workshop	23
17	Zagreb Workshop	27

LIST OF TABLES

TABLE	TITLE	PAGE
01	Early evaluation planning for DWS activities.	13
02	Risk detection items regarding evaluation tasks.	13
03	Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS1.	17
04	Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS2.	18
05	Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS3.	18
06	Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS4.	19

1. INTRODUCTION

Producing a valid and vibrant evaluation for the many dimensions of a socio-technical process constitutes an exciting and tricky enterprise. As Land (2000) said, the “**problem of evaluation**” is witnessed by “the difficulties encountered by researchers and practitioners in accounting ex post for the benefits accruing to the organization from the development of information systems”. It was only at the end of the ‘90s researchers provided evidence that investments in ICT are positive for organizations’ productivity: optimistic findings are still subject to argument and controversy.

With PIE News the problem of evaluation is even more complicated. The “public design” character of the project represents an additional difficulty: How to properly measure the project success without leveraging on organizational productivity? How to acquire relevant results in time in order to produce adequate and sustainable incentives and improvement mechanisms at the public space level?

The PIE News project evaluation plan leverages on the early plan contained in the project proposal and on the participatory activity of plan refinement and validation that involved – and continuously involves – the project partners with the coordination of the evaluation leader (CN). As visualized in Figure 1 the plan – which presents the most recent version and may be subject to further revisions – is composed by **heterogeneous elements all subject to preparation, execution and follow-up work:**

- ▶ activities that are planned and/or executed leveraging on design workshops (DWSs) tasks;
- ▶ project deliverables regarding evaluation planning and reporting;
- ▶ project milestones regarding risk detection and its possible reduction.

Figure 4: A timeline vision of PIE News evaluation activities.

Evaluation activities in PIE News are therefore **strictly connected to the community awareness platform design/implementation activities**, sharing the co-working process mainly through the participation of project partners and platform users to DWSs in the pilot sites. Online activities including conference calls, chat messaging, emails and

document co-writing will be also very important for the participatory definition and execution of evaluation tasks, but DWSs (and project meetings in general) will be considered as the central point for consortium decisions regarding evaluation tasks.

The **evaluation objectives** for PIE News are to provide:

- ▶ a detailed plan defined in participation with project partners;
- ▶ self-evaluation of pilots' activities;
- ▶ evaluation of the MockUps and platform releases at the pilot level;
- ▶ feedback with level of satisfaction and comments from users and stakeholders after every activity - involving external people - at the pilot level;
- ▶ sustain the evolution of social networks' topology by leveraging on Network Dynamics monitoring and on web/social channels participation monitoring;
- ▶ useful deliverables, reports and more or less formal guidelines for PIE News improvements;
- ▶ some selected evaluation results published online as "evaluation dashboard".

The evaluation plan has been created with the aim to acquire the maximum information from project partners, platform

users and project stakeholders in general. The main reason for its incremental/integrated/participative character is to engage involved people in sustainable activities in order to minimize the burden for external people (users and stakeholders) and also for project partners.

In order to describe the evaluation activities that comprise the plan, **this document is organized as follows**: Chapter 2 provides the early evaluation plan elements and the practical approach agreed by project partners for the participatory co-definition and co-working of evaluation activities; Chapter 3 presents the detailed plan regarding the workshops-related evaluation activities; Chapter 4 enters in detail on some specific evaluation activities like satisfaction surveys, network dynamics analysis, project web/social channels analytics, and the intermediate and final self-assessment; Chapter 5 exemplifies the participated evaluation planning and co-working by presenting the Early Users' Survey preparation; finally, the Conclusions will summarize the many open issues regarding evaluation that will need to be further discussed and defined within the consortium. The reader will also find in Annexes the four versions of the Early User Survey questionnaire (English, Italian, Dutch, Croatian) in the Lime Survey printing structure.

2. FROM THE EARLY PLANNING TO A PRACTICAL APPROACH

Fig. 05

During the first months of the project, the PIE News Evaluation Plan has been developed from the early evaluation planning contained in the project proposal to the more detailed and practical evaluation plan. Following the project participatory framework, some new elements of the plan have been initially discussed during the KOM while a more organic evaluation proposal has been presented and

discussed within the consortium during DWS1 in Zagreb.

This section presents (1) the main elements of the evaluation early plan contained in the PIE News project proposal, then (2) the project evaluation approach agreed with the project partners in Zagreb – while the elements will be described in the next chapters.

2.1 EARLY PLANNING FROM THE PROJECT PROPOSAL

Figure 6: Design workshops-related evaluation activities' early planning.

2.1.1 Main evaluation components and tools

The PIE News evaluation plan leverages on four main evaluation components:

I. DWS-related activities: the main place for project evaluation activities are the project design workshops, where offline analysis will mainly leverage on focus groups and other methodologies (e.g.: questionnaires or other forms of written feedback) involving pilot partners, which constitute an essential gateway to

platform users and stakeholders. See Section 2.1.2 for the early workshop planning, and Chapter 3 for a detailed plan of workshops' evaluation activities.

II. Platform web logs/analytics and social networks analytics: on-line data relevant to the evaluation of the adoption and use of the PIE News platform will be extracted from the platform logs and analytics. For example, specific analytics from the project social networks will be used in order to understand the users' involvement. For a more detailed description of this evaluation component see Section 4.3.

III. Network dynamics analysis: additional on-line data regarding the topological evolution of the PIE News online networks will be extracted from the project social networks as a result of the Task 4.4 activities that will integrate into the platform the algorithms elaborated in Task 3.4. Analysis of these data will (i) allow a more or less continuous evaluation of the users' level of engagement through appropriate analytics and machine learning tools, and (ii) provide an appropriate analytic dashboard to report on current trends and system dynamics. For a more detailed description of planned network dynamics analysis see Section 4.2.

IV. Final evaluation activities: some final off-line activities will involve project partners as well as platform users and stakeholders in order to perform a final PIE News evaluation report.

2.1.2 Early workshops plan

At an early stage the focus group objectives to be fulfilled during the project DWSs have been defined as described in Table 1.

WORKSHOP NO.	ACTIVITIES
DWS1 (M2)	Evaluation plan validation
DWS2 (M6)	Self-evaluation of pilots' activities
DWS3 (M13)	Self-evaluation of pilots' activities Pilots evaluation of reputation and currency solutions Pilots training: MockUp2 user feedback
DWS4 (M21)	Self-evaluation of pilots' activities Pilots evaluation of collaborative economy and sustainability solutions Pilots training: MockUp3 user feedback Planning 3rd and Final Release user feedback activities

Table 1: Early evaluation planning for DWS activities.

2.1.3 Main deadlines

The project evaluation task is subject to the following main deadlines:

- ▶ **D5.1 «Evaluation Plan»** – (M6)
- ▶ **D5.3 «Evaluation Report»** – (M36)
- ▶ **MS10 «Risk Detection Internal Report I** – (M18)
- ▶ **MS14 «Risk Detection Internal Report II** – (M30)
- ▶ **Online updated Dashboard with evaluation results** – during the 2nd year of the project

2.1.4 Key Process Indicators

Within the project proposal KPIs there are at least three that are closely involved with evaluation tasks and that will

be kept in particular consideration by evaluation activities:

- ▶ **[KPI 4] Users involved in evaluation (M36): 150 for each pilot**
- ▶ **[KPI 7] Users of the mobile version (M36): 1000**
- ▶ **[KPI 8] Platform interactions (M36): 50000 (stories, comments, sharing ...)**

2.1.5 Risk detection evaluation-related issues

Within the project proposal Risk Detection issues there are at least five that are closely involved with WP5 evaluation task (Table 2), and that will be considered for the Risk Detection reports.

DESCRIPTION OF RISK	PROBABILITY / IMPACT	PROPOSED RISK-MITIGATION MEASURES
Technological illiteracy target groups	L/M	Training during pilot sessions
Limited access to the internet/mobile	L/M	Collaborations (bars, libraries...) for free WiFi & tools
Privacy and distrust	L/H	Privacy-by-design, data control, reputation mechanisms
Failure in mobilising stakeholders	L/M	Partners' networks & supporting letters
Failure in gaining sustainability	M/H	Monitor relations in pilots & networks in order to engage in alternative sustainability models

Table 2: Risk detection items regarding evaluation tasks.

2.2 PRACTICAL APPROACH TO EVALUATION

The PIE News project leverages on a participatory framework that gradually will co-define the evaluation activities at the detailed level as a result of consortium discussions and agreements. The following elements addressing our approach to the evaluation activities in practice have been presented, discussed and agreed by partners during the DWS1 in Zagreb.

2.2.1 Incremental & integrated

- ▶ **Incremental.** The Evaluation Plan and its elements will be gradually developed and refined over time with the help of project partners.

Figure 7: The incremental character of PIE News evaluation planning.

- ▶ **Integrated.** At the practical level, some evaluation tasks will leverage upon project activities, e.g. platform design and research at the pilot level activities. This means that, especially for qualitative analysis (interviews, focus groups...) involving users and stakeholders – where it is important to interact in local language and to avoid the proliferation of interactions aiming to minimize the burden on participants -, evaluation activities will be merged with design ones.

Figure 8: The integrated character of PIE News evaluation activities.

Fig. 09

2.2.2 Participative & sustainable

- ▶ **Participative.** PIE News evaluation plan and activities will be created and performed with the involvement of project partners.
- ▶ **Sustainable.** Co-working on evaluation plan and activities must be sustainable for everyone, not only for platform users. Therefore, the needs of project partners, users and stakeholders will be taken under high consideration.

2.2.3 Consortium agreement on the participative approach

Project partners agreed on the following rules for co-working on evaluation activities:

- 1. Activity opening** with basic idea and requirements, by the evaluation leader.
- 2. Consortium needs and team creation:**
 - Requirements elicitation
 - Sustainability validation
 - Co-working for both planning and activities
- 3. Reviews:**
 - Team internal, with changes
 - Consortium, with last validation

In case of complications and/or last minute decisions, the project top-down hierarchical approach will be adopted: project, WP and task leaders will have the last word.

2.2.4 Starting with the unplanned Early User Survey (EUS)

The PIE News “Early User Survey” (EUS) is an evaluation-related activity which was not planned in the project proposal, but that has been identified as crucial - for the best project start - at the beginning of M1 by the Research

and Innovation Coordinator and the Evaluation Leader. It represents the flexible approach embraced by the project consortium targeting meaningful activities instead of following the early planning. The EUS activities have been initially discussed and agreed by project partners during the KOM for a rapid start of this participative task. An exhaustive description of the EUS planning phase is available in Chapter 5.

2.2.5 Visual dissemination of evaluation results

An up-to-date public on-line **evaluation dashboard** with metrics for services improvement will be created during the second year of the project and then it will be implemented and improved until the end of the project. The evaluation dashboard will take place on the PIE News project website as a webpage with evaluation data in temporal order (the latest on the top of the page).

The contents displayed on the dashboard will be selected by a team composed by the PL, the RIC and the evaluation leader. The graphical dimension will leverage on the contribution of the UNITN visual designer and its standards will be defined during the second year of the project. Two examples follow:

- ▶ **RADAR CHART:** radar charts are often used to map multiple variables at the same time. The example in Figure 6 uses three poles to visualize the amount of income, poverty and unemployment among the three pilots. The length of the segments depends on the weight of the represented value. In general, there could be more poles, and, often the center is 0 and the highest value is on the outer circle. Radar charts are particularly useful in showing how different individual entities compare on multiple characteristics.

Figure 10: Example of radar chart for the PIE News evaluation dashboard.

- ▶ **STACKED BAR CHART:** in the Figure 7 example below, a stacked bar chart has been implemented to visualize the PIE conditions distributions according to the ages of the platform users. The stacked bar chart allows the comparison of several values and their sub-composition at the same time. Human vision has less difficulties in comparing straight lines than circular sectors, for this reason a stacked bar chart is more used than pie charts. Stacked bar charts are particularly useful in allowing comparison of frequencies of particular values or features across a group, rather than differences between individuals.

Figure 11: Example of stacked bar chart for the PIE News evaluation dashboard.

3. WORKSHOP-RELATED EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

Fig. 12

3.1 INTRODUCTION

As introduced previously, design workshops (DWSs) are the core place for off-line evaluation activities in co-working

with project partners. Figure 8 shows how PIE News evaluation leverages on the four design workshops – plus the final evaluation phase - in order to acquire evaluation data from pilots and project partners.

Figure 13: The evaluation activities leveraging on PIE News design workshops.

The **aim of this chapter** is to provide a detailed description of partners' agreements on DWSs evaluation-related activities, as resulted from the consortium discussion during the DWS1 in Zagreb. For every DWS we present:

Given the participatory, integrated and incremental character of the evaluation plan, some evaluation activities will need to be further discussed and defined by the consortium as the project progresses.

- ▶ The evaluation-related activities with a brief presentation.
- ▶ A plan of sub-tasks relating the activities to be performed before, during and after the workshop.

3.2 PARTNERS' AGREEMENT ON EVALUATION-RELATED ACTIVITIES AT DWSS

3.2.1 DWS1 – M3: September 2016

The following activities have been executed by project partners:

DWS1.1: Evaluation Plan: detailed proposal validation

During DWS1, the Evaluation Plan has been discussed and validated by the project partners. Some specific

BEFORE	Evaluation Plan: detailed proposal preparation (CN)
	Early Users' Survey: first draft preparation as a result of partners' co-working (CN)
DURING	Evaluation Plan: discussion and validation (ALL)
	Early Users' Survey: validation (ALL)
AFTER	Evaluation Plan: survey preparation & Platform integration at M8 (CN)
	Early Users' Survey: analysis (CN)

Table 3: Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS1.

3.2.2 DWS2 – M7: January 2017

The following activities have been agreed by project partners:

DWS2.1: User Registration Survey (URS): agreements

The User Registration Survey (URS), if it will be confirmed as a relevant task for evaluation purposes, will probably have the following characters (to be confirmed):

- ▶ Objective: to acquire platform users' data starting from the first mobile release of the platform, scheduled in February 2017.
- ▶ Questionnaire: created by leveraging – and expanding – the Early User Survey for data comparison purposes.
- ▶ Build upon the PIE News instantiation of the Lime Survey tool.

The URS also follows the intention to avoid data-treatment related risk by acquiring and managing separately two sources of information about the user: (a) platform user profiling, with alias and – hidden – email, and (b) sensible but useful data.

A team composed of the PC, the PL, the RIC and the evaluation leader will start discussing it in December 2016 with the aim to answer the following issues: Is the URS relevant for the project? If yes, why? Who will participate in the URS activities and how?

DWS2.2: Self-evaluation of pilots' activities

The self-evaluation of pilots' activities is a strategic and continuous task for PIE News that will drive the consortium to the Final Evaluation activity. For this reason,

responsibilities were taken and some points were identified for further elaboration, following the incremental approach.

DWS1.2: Early Users' Survey: final discussion and validation

During DWS1, pilot partners had the opportunity to analyze the four language-specific questionnaires. As a result, it was decided to proceed with a further improvement of the survey and with a subsequent delay of its delivery to users.

self-evaluation activities will need to be conducted in a systematic way.

A team composed of the PL, the RIC and the evaluation leader is defining a quality proposal for this task to be discussed and validated by project partners and pilot ones in particular. The idea is to leverage on the Self-Assessment Toolkit (SAT) offered by the IA4SI project for assessing the multidimensional impacts of the PIE News project. Further information on this tool is presented in Chapter 4.5.

DWS2.3: Planning MockUps' user feedback activities

Feedback from the platform users on MockUps constitute crucial evaluation activities for PIE News. During DWS2, the evaluation activities for MockUp2 (DWS3) and MockUp3 (DWS4) will be planned with project partners.

Fig. 14

BEFORE	User Registration Survey: define the survey basics (TEAM) evaluation categories and translations (ALL) and Lime Survey instantiation on project HW (CN)
	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: framework preparation (TEAM/PILOTS) and validation (PILOTS/ALL)
	Planning MockUps' user feedback activities: planning preparation (CN)
DURING	User Registration Survey: last agreements on the survey campaign
	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: focus group using the Self-Assessment Toolkit
	Planning MockUps' user feedback activities: discussion and planning
AFTER	User Registration Survey: survey refinement & Platform integration at M8 (CN)
	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: analysis (CN)
	Planning MockUps' user feedback activities: implementation of procedures (CN)

Table 4: Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS2.

3.2.3 DWS3 – M13: July 2017

The following activities have been agreed by project partners:

DWS3.1: Self-evaluation of pilots' activities

Pilots' activities self-evaluation is a strategic and continuous task for PIE News that will drive the consortium to the Final Evaluation task. For this reason, self-evaluation activities will need to be conducted in a systematic way.

Following the preparation activities planned for DWS2, the idea is to leverage on the Self-Assessment Toolkit (SAT) offered by the IA4SI project for assessing the multidimensional impacts of the PIE News project. Further information on this tool is presented in Chapter 4.4.

DWS3.2: Pilots' evaluation of reputation and currency solutions

The plan is to agree with Pilot leaders during the DWS preparation phase on the best way to acquire platform/MockUp evaluation data from users and stakeholders.

- ▶ The idea is to leverage as much as possible on design activities and already planned focus groups in order to avoid the proliferation of new activities and the subsequent over-involvement of users.

- ▶ Data collection activities from users will be mediated/performed by Pilot leaders with the facilitation of the evaluation leader, the PL and the RIC.

- ▶ The aim is to collect data before or during the DWS, or immediately after it.

DWS3.3: MockUp2 User Feedback

The user feedback elicitation on the last platform MockUp delivered by PIE News constitutes a core activity for the project. Since (i) MockUp evaluation tasks start at the DWS3 level and (ii) the consortium needs to figure out the procedures of other evaluation tasks, the feedback on MockUp2 will be acquired through procedures that will be discussed and defined with the involvement of project partners during DWS2. As for other evaluation activities:

- ▶ The idea is to leverage as much as possible on design activities and already planned focus groups in order to avoid the proliferation of new activities and the subsequent over-involvement of users.

- ▶ Data collection activities from users will be mediated/performed by Pilot leaders with the facilitation of the evaluation leader, the PL and the RIC.

- ▶ The aim is to collect data before or during the DWS, or immediately after it.

BEFORE	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: framework preparation (TEAM) and validation (PILOTS/ALL)
	Pilots evaluation of reputation and currency solutions: preparation (CN)
	MockUp2 User Feedback: preparation (CN)
DURING	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: focus group using the Self-Assessment Toolkit
	Pilots evaluation of reputation and currency solutions: preparation and last agreements for the evaluation campaign (if data no already collected at pilot level)
	MockUp2 User Feedback: preparation and last agreement for evaluation campaign (if data no already collected at pilot level)
AFTER	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: analysis (CN)
	Pilots evaluation of reputation and currency solutions: evaluation campaign (Pilots) and data analysis (CN)
	MockUp2 User Feedback: evaluation campaign (Pilots) and data analysis (CN)

Table 5: Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS3.

3.2.4 DWS4 – M21: March 2018

The following activities have been agreed by the project partners:

DWS4.1: Self-evaluation of pilots’ activities

Pilots’ self-evaluation is a strategic and continuous task for PIE News that will drive the consortium to the Final Evaluation task. For this reason, self-evaluation activities will need to be conducted in a systematic way.

Following the preparation activities planned for DWS2, the idea is to leverage on the Self-Assessment Toolkit (SAT) offered by the IA4SI project for assessing the multidimensional impacts of the PIE News project. Further information about this tool is presented in Chapter 4.4.

DWS4.2: Pilots’ evaluation of collaborative economy and sustainability solutions

As for the DWS3.2 task, the plan is to agree with Pilot leaders during the DWS preparation phase on the best way to acquire platform/MockUp evaluation data from users and stakeholders.

- ▶ The idea is to leverage as much as possible on design activities and already planned focus groups in order to avoid the proliferation of new activities and the subsequent over-involvement of users.
- ▶ Data collection activities from users will be mediated/performed by Pilot leaders with the facilitation of the evaluation leader, the PL and the RIC.

- ▶ The aim is to collect data before or during the DWS, or immediately after it.

DWS4.3: MockUp3 User Feedback

Like the MockUp2 evaluation task, the feedback on MockUp3 will be acquired through procedures that will be discussed and defined with the involvement of project partners during DWS2. As for other evaluation activities:

- ▶ The idea is to leverage as much as possible on design activities and already planned focus groups in order to avoid the proliferation of new activities and the subsequent over-involvement of users.
- ▶ Data collection activities from users will be mediated/performed by Pilot leaders with the facilitation of the evaluation leader, the PL and the RIC.
- ▶ The aim is to collect data before or during the DWS, or immediately after it.

DWS4.4: Planning user feedback activities on 3rd and Final Releases

The last two users’ feedback activities considered on the early evaluation plan, on the third and final platform releases, will be discussed and scheduled during the DWS4 preparation and execution phases.

BEFORE	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: framework preparation (TEAM) and validation (PILOTS/ALL)
	Pilots evaluation of collaborative economy and sustainability solutions: preparation (CN)
	MockUp3 User Feedback Survey: preparation (CN)
	Planning user feedback activities on 3rd and Final Releases: preparation (CN)
DURING	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: focus group with use of Self-Assessment Toolkit
	Pilots’ evaluation of collaborative economy and sustainability solutions: preparation and last agreements for the evaluation campaign (if data not already collected at pilot level)
	MockUp3 User Feedback Survey: preparation and last agreement for evaluation campaign (if data no already collected at pilot level)
	Planning user feedback activities on 3rd and Final Releases: discussion and agreement
AFTER	Self-evaluation of Pilots activities: analysis (CN)
	Pilots evaluation of collaborative economy and sustainability solutions: evaluation campaign (Pilots) and data analysis (CN)
	MockUp3 User Feedback Survey: evaluation campaign (Pilots) and data analysis (CN)
	Planning user feedback activities on 3rd and Final Releases: 3R & FR evaluation campaigns (Pilots & CN)

Table 6: Evaluation-related work before/during/after DWS4.

4. FOCUS ON SOME SPECIFIC EVALUATION ACTIVITIES

This chapter will discuss in depth some specific evaluation activities, including activities that are not related to workshops as well as those that are.

4.1 USER-STAKEHOLDER SATISFACTION SURVEY (USSS)

4.1.1 Introduction and aim

During DWS1 in Zagreb, the project partners agreed on the idea to run a very brief “user satisfaction survey” after every structured interaction with the user. Given the various possible structured interactions (workshops, interviews, ...) with a larger group of stakeholders at the pilot level (associations, institutions ...), the idea is here to enlarge the survey target by including both the users’ and the stakeholders’ sides.

4.1.2 Strategy

- ▶ The USSS is a very important qualitative and post-activity evaluation action for PIE News, but this tool needs to be designed so as to minimize the burden on users. Anticipating repeatedly having to complete an overly-detailed or complex survey would be likely to discourage participants from future participation on the site.
- ▶ Partners required (DWS1) that the satisfaction survey **needs to:**
 - be as short as possible: one satisfaction answer (Likert scale) and one comment/suggestion (open text);
 - have the minimum impact in terms of user/stakeholder involvement;
 - have the minimum impact in terms of pilot partners’ involvement.
- ▶ A survey **template** will be created with the minimum involvement of project partners (e.g.: translations) and

then it will be **adapted to specific situations** by the evaluation leader.

- ▶ Both the survey template and specific instantiations will be created on Lime Survey, trying to follow the project visual guidelines in the best way.
- ▶ The template will have the following **structure:**
 - **TITLE:** specific for the pilot-specific activity.
 - **INTRODUCTION:** brief reminder of the PIE News project and feedback request.
 - **USER CONSENT:** anonymous data for platform/project improvement and project/scientific aims.
 - **Q1 - SATISFACTION:** 1-5 Likert scale.
 - **Q2 - COMMENT/SUGGESTION:** open text.
 - **END MESSAGE:** with also main project links (website, platforms, socials).
- ▶ **Pilot partners will be asked for minimal involvement** in this activity:
 - Help the evaluation leader with survey template translations, if needed.
 - Communicate to the evaluation leader about local activities requiring a satisfaction survey in sufficient time (at least 10 days before) for its discussion and preparation.
 - Help the evaluation leader with pilot-specific text for the specific survey preparation (e.g.: title and introduction).
 - Disseminate the survey link to the users/stakeholders with the activity report (in the mail and/or in the document) and push them for participation.
 - Translate into English the open text answers.

Fig. 15

4.2 NETWORK DYNAMICS ANALYSIS (NDA)

Another core evaluation activity is the analysis of the on-line network dynamics involved by project platform and social media. The evolution of the topology of every social network is a key aspect for engaging users' participation. **The idea of the Network Dynamics Analysis (NDA) applied to PIE News evaluation tasks is to leverage on NDA in order to maintain a critical and sustainable mass of users.** For instance, it will be possible to adopt mechanisms like “incentive design” of user management tools and “cooperative schemes” for online advertisements.

Project NDA research is in its early stages. Within WP4, partners are involved in discussion on some aspects related to the design of information architecture and functionalities of the PIE news platform. Indeed, **in order to conduct a network dynamics analysis and provide algorithms for dissemination and engagement, two crucial aspects need to be taken in consideration:**

1. Network structure induced by the platform: depending on the components we implement, we can attain different structures, and different interactions. News may reach everyone and users act as a broadcast channel. If we have chats directly connecting users, links are created, and messages may diffuse in a peer to peer fashion. If we leverage on Twitter, there is a structure which is inherited from the leader-follower network structure which is specific of Twitter. A timeline for posting to each user the news of interest may result in a Facebook-style platform: this feature is far beyond what we promised, but could be a feature we keep as a “theoretical” enabler which may add in the future of the platform. Groups on Facebook could be linked to the website and communities could be tracked also at that level.

2. Messages: there will likely be “institutional” messages which are pre-filtered and studied in order to be accessible by the most users. Other type of messages may be private messages or visible only to a minority or specific community in the platform (e.g., due to language). Finally, if we have emails this could result in a specific type of offline communication.

More specific direction on NDA research and its application to project evaluation task will be further developed through the collaboration of WP3, WP4 and WP5.

4.3 GOOGLE ANALYTICS, FACEBOOK INSIGHTS AND HASHTAG ANALYTICS

Web and social networks analytics are a relevant source of data for process and technology evaluation. Considering the web tools created and adopted by PIE News and the possible restrictions imposed by the forthcoming Data-Management Plan (D1.2), the idea is to adopt the following web monitoring

tools for project evaluation purposes:

- ▶ **Website analytics / logs:** Google Analytics will be adopted in order to monitor the project website use and obtain data for evaluation purposes. In case of particular need also web logs will be analyzed.
- ▶ **Platform analytics / logs:** unfortunately, Google Analytics collides with restrictions imposed by the project data-management plan. Therefore, the monitoring of the platform will be performed by leveraging on Piwik¹ which is a free and open-source web analytics application. Like Google Analytics, Piwik works through platform integration but it is in line with the project data-management restrictions. As on the institutional website no action by the visitor is required and, therefore, there is no sharing of sensitive information, we have adopted the most cost-effective solution. On the platform, we have decided to adopt the solution that better protect people using the platform and sharing their data or stories. In case of particular need, web logs may also be analyzed.
- ▶ **Facebook Insights:** regarding the PieNewsCommonfare page on Facebook, the Insights function will be used in order to gather evaluation data.
- ▶ **Twitter analytics and other monitoring tools for hashtag use:** regarding #commonfare, the Twitter analytics will be used in order to monitor the hashtag diffusion, in addition to other hashtag monitoring tools that need to be defined.
- ▶ **YouTube analytics:** regarding the YouTube channel with project videos, YouTube analytics will be used for monitoring purposes.

4.4 INTERMEDIATE AND FINAL SELF-ASSESSMENT

Probably the most relevant evaluation tasks for PIE News are the continuous and the final self-evaluation of the many project dimensions. In the PIE News plan it involves:

- ▶ the “**self-evaluation of pilots' activities**” (see three evaluation activities in Chapter 3.1: DWS2.2, DWS3.1 and DWS4.1);
- ▶ the “**final evaluation activities**” (See Section 2.1.1) involving both project partners (“final self-evaluation activities”) and external entities such as platform users and project stakeholders at the pilot level (“final evaluation activities”).

The idea is to proceed with intermediate and final self-assessment in a systematic way by leveraging on the **Self-Assessment Toolkit (SAT)** offered by the IA4SI project² for assessing the multidimensional impacts of the PIE News project. This tool helps CAPS projects to assess their socio-economic, environmental and political impacts and results are visualized in concise and user-friendly way.

¹ <https://piwik.org/>

² <http://ia4si.eu/>

By logging on to the SAT each project finds a list of questions to be answered in order to assess projects' impacts. The tool needs to be adequately tailored for the specific project and purposes, then the PL and/or the RIC will need to set the SAT for the specific PIE News needs at the beginning of the process. It is a longitudinal evaluation tool, meaning that we can start working on it in order to produce intermediate and final assessments! It involves self-assessment activities for project partners and external entities like platform users and pilot stakeholders. The IA4SI team follows and helps the process providing the needed support.

The tool is composed of five main sections: input, output, impacts, assessment, report. The "Impacts" section is organized in four areas: social, political, economical, environmental. It is at this stage that project/evaluation leaders will have the chance to organize personalized multidimensional assessment leveraging on the dimensions

more relevant for the PIE News project (Bellini, Passani, Klitsi and Vanobberger, 2016).

The practical execution of self-assessment activities needs to be further discussed and defined. For sure it will leverage upon focus-groups involving project (especially pilot) partners during project DWSSs. It is also possible that users and stakeholders will be asked not to directly interact with the SAT tool, performing instead with them specific focus groups or interviews in order to acquire the needed information. The involvement of pilot leaders in user/stakeholder interaction activities will be necessary for language needs. Interaction with users and stakeholders for evaluation purposes will be probably performed within the design research framework and integrated with other activities, in order to reduce to the minimum the number of interaction with them.

5. AN EXAMPLE: THE EARLY USER SURVEY PREPARATION

Fig. 16

The PIE News “Early User Survey” (EUS) is an evaluation-related activity which was not planned in the project proposal, but that has been identified as crucial – for the best project start – at the beginning of M1 by the Research and Innovation Coordinator and the WP5 Leader.

This activity was possible because during the KOM a partners’ team was involved in its creation, spending a considerable and unexpected amount of effort between July–October 2016, often working during holidays.

The survey is grounded in the adoption of a subjective understanding of the term “precarious”, as a condition and not as a contractual status. This means that one can be precarious even with a permanent work contract, because the many possible dimensions of uncertainty (e.g.: employer under risk, crisis of the job market) drive an objective or perceived feeling of individual precariousness. The more complex understanding of the precarious experience will probably be a project outcome.

5.1 OBJECTIVES, STRUCTURE AND STRATEGY

The following **objectives** have been identified for the EUS:

1. Collect a rapid first image of possible users, which could differ from Pilot partners’ statistical expectations. It also pre-filters possible platform users: who is willing to use ICTs.
2. Start informing users about the project.
3. Start understanding the number of users willing to participate the design/evaluation phases.

The survey is composed of a multilingual (English, Dutch, Croatian, Italian) questionnaire with the following **structure**:

- ▶ **INTRODUCTION:** brief project presentation and questionnaire intro.
- ▶ **USER CONSENT:** user +18 and agreement on anonymous data use for project/partners scientific purposes.
- ▶ **QUESTIONNAIRE:** 16 questions (17 with the User Consent one).
- ▶ **END MESSAGE:** with also project Website and Facebook page links.

Also the survey **strategy** has been approved by the Scientific Coordinator and then discussed and agreed during the KOM with project partners:

- ▶ Short (maximum 10-18 questions) and easy to answer (only single or multiple choices) questionnaire to foster the maximum participation. A longer survey will enrich platform registration at M8.
- ▶ Based on demographic questions. With very little “technology use” and “ask for participation” questions.
- ▶ Use Eurostat metrics for future comparison, when possible.
- ▶ Do not acquire personal sensitive data: no objective data but subjective perception when needed.
- ▶ Skipping questions disabled to acquire the maximum data: it is not really unfair since it will be short, easy and no sensitive data will be present.
- ▶ The survey is anonymous.
- ▶ Use “Lime Survey” tool through the UNITN installation. A PIE News installation on Lime Survey will be created later on for further project surveys. This choice meets the possibility to create high level survey with a Free/OpenSource/DataSafety project service. The UNITN installation does not allow the creation of a survey with project visual identity guidelines.
- ▶ Project Partners (especially pilot leaders) take care of the electronic distribution of the questionnaire.
- ▶ The collective distribution of participation links affects

the possibility to use “tokens” which would be useful in order to reach specific users for reminders also in the case of autonomous answers survey.

5.2 PARTICIPATORY PROCESS

The survey was elaborated and conducted following a participatory process agreed by project partners:

- I. First questionnaire idea: early July (CN, MITI)
- II. Presentation and co-working agreements: KOM (all)
- III. English questionnaire co-creation: late July (all)
- IV. Translation: August (Pilots)
- V. Creation of the online survey – first round: early September (CN)
- VI. Validation and agreements: DWS1, the 22nd of September (all)
- VII. Last review of the survey with new questions and translations: late September (all)
- VIII. Creation of the online survey – second round: early October (CN)
- IX. Participation links internal distribution: 7th October (CN)
- X. Internal participation test: 7-10 October (all)
- XI. Survey opening with active participation links: 10-26 October
 - a. Participation links ready for online distribution and reminders: 10th October (all)
 - b. Participation check and communication to partners: 13th October (CN)
 - c. Participation check and communication to partners: 17th October (CN)
 - d. Participation check and communication to partners: 20th October (CN)
 - e. Participation check, communication to partners and survey closure: 26th October (CN)
- XII. Analysis: November (CN)
- XIII. Results circulation: December 2016 (CN)
- XIV. Discussion on the survey results and further decisions: during DWS2, in January 2017 (all)

5.3 THE ENGLISH QUESTIONNAIRE

This section represents the English questionnaire of the Early User Survey while the four language versions of the Lime Survey printed questionnaire are in Annexes. Please

note that the on-line survey embodied both filters and hidden questions' codes while in off-line transcriptions both filters and questions' codes are visible. (* = answer requested)

5.3.1 Introduction

PIE News is a project financed by the European Community within the H2020-ICT-2015 Program (nr.: 687922).

For the next 3 years, we will work with people in Italy, Croatia and the Netherlands to foster alternative and more equal models of wealth distribution in Europe, discussing everyday life problems, encouraging common participatory solutions and trying to influence public policies.

Please help us by investing 2 minutes of your time and answering the following questions. This will help PIE News start one project activity.

The questionnaire is anonymous!

There are 16 questions in this survey.

5.3.2 User consent

Q1. I am 18+ years old and I AGREE to the anonymous use - and only in aggregated form - of my answers for the PIE News project and further activities such as publications:

[Single choice]*

- A1. Yes
- A2. No (in this case the data collected would be unusable and the questionnaire may stop here)

[END Message]

5.3.3 Questionnaire

Q1. RESIDENCE: [Single choice]*

- A1. Italy
- A2. Croatia
- A3. Netherlands
- A4. Other

Q2.GENDER: [Single choice]*

- A1. Male
- A2. Female
- A3. None of the above

Q3. AGE: [Single choice]*

- A1. 70+
- A2. 65-69
- A3. 60-64
- A4. 55-59
- A5. 50-54
- A6. 45-49
- A7. 40-44
- A8. 35-39
- A9. 30-34
- A10. 25-29
- A11. 20-24
- A12. 19-18

Q4. RESPONSIBLE FOR children and/or other persons:

[Single choice]*

- A1. 0
- A2. 1
- A3. 2
- A4. 3
- A5. 4
- A6. 5+

Q5. EDUCATION LEVEL: [Single choice]*

- A1. Primary school
- A2. Professional school
- A3. High school/Secondary school
- A4. Bachelor
- A5. Master
- A6. Doctoral

Q6. PROFESSIONAL SECTOR, main one: [Single choice]*

- A1. Mining and quarrying.
- A2. Manufacturing.
- A3. Electricity, gas, steam and air cond. supply.
- A4. Water supply, waste and remediation.
- A5. Construction.
- A6. Distributive trades.
- A7. Transport and storage.
- A8. Accommodation and food services.
- A9. Information and communication.
- A10. Real estate activities.
- A11. Professional, scientific and technical.
- A12. Administrative and support services (including cultural, education and health).
- A13. Repair: computer, personal and household goods

Q7. EMPLOYMENT LEVEL, currently I am: [Single choice]*

- A1. Fully employed
- A2. Partially employed
- A3. Unemployed
- A4. Retired
- A5. Other

Q8. PRECARIOUS CONDITION, currently I am: [Single choice]*

- A1. Precarious [Q9]
- A2. Not precarious [Q12]

Q9. PRECARIOUS WORKER type, currently I am: [Single choice]*

- A1. Employed [Q10]
- A2. Independent worker / self-employed [Q11]
- A3. I do not work (e.g.: in-between temporary jobs) [Q12]

Q10. As EMPLOYED, currently I am: [Multiple choice]*

- A1. Temporary worker
- A2. Temporary intermediated employee
- A3. Permanent position worker
- A4. Part-time worker
- A5. Double part-time worker
- A6. Full-time worker
- A7. Other (internship, training ...) [Q12]

Q11. As INDEPENDENT WORKER, currently I am: [Single choice]*

- A1. Self-employed / free-lancer
- A2. Collaborator and/or member of a cooperative firm

- A3. Zero-hour worker (fits with UK and Netherlands)
- A4. Artisan
- A5. Entrepreneur
- A6. Other (occasional ...)

Q12. How would you describe your FINANCIAL CONDITION? [Single choice]*

- A1. Poor
- A2. Slightly poor
- A3. Comfortable
- A4. Slightly rich
- A5. Rich

Q13. TECHNOLOGIES, which one do you use for on-line information and communication? [Multiple choice]*

- A1. Desktop / Laptop
- A2. Tablet
- A3. Smartphone
- A4. Other (XBox, SmartTV...)

Q14. SOCIAL MEDIA, which one do you use more? [Likert scale: 1min-5max]*

- 1. Facebook
- 2. Twitter
- 3. LinkedIn
- 4. Snapchat
- 5. Instagram
- 6. Youtube
- 7. Other

Q15. Would you be interested in PARTICIPATING in the activities of the PIE News project [Website link], particularly its on-line platform aiming to provide users with information and resources to improve economic and life conditions? [Single choice]*

- A1. Not at all [Q16]
- A2. No [Q16]
- A3. Maybe [END Message]
- A4. Yes [END Message]
- A5. Definitely [END Message]

Q16. If “no” or “not at all”, why? [Single choice]*

- A1. Because I do not believe in the project effectiveness
- A2. Because I do not believe in the importance of the project
- A3. Because I do not need it
- A4. Because I am not interested in such topics
- A5. Because I do not have time to participate

5.3.4 End message

Thank you!

The PIE News platform will be ready starting from February 2017 with basic functionalities.

In the meantime, feel free to follow us on the project website (www.pienews.eu) and on Facebook (PieNewsCommonfare).

5.4 LINKS FOR THE COMPARISON OF RESULTS.

In order to facilitate the comparison of results, the metrics of three questions refer to international choices:

- ▶ Q3 (AGE): EUROSTAT Population 1994 and 2014³.
- ▶ Q5 (EDUCATION LEVEL): as a simplification of the UNESCO ISCED 2011⁴ – International Standard Classification of Education.
- ▶ Q6 (PROFESSIONAL SECTOR): EUROSTAT⁵.

5.5 PROTECTION OF PERSONAL DATA.

The Early User Survey development anticipated the creation of a PIE News ethical and data protection protocol. For this reason, we took in consideration the “seven principles governing the OECD’s recommendations for protection of personal data” (Shimanek 2001):

- 1) Notice: data subjects should be given notice when their data is being collected;
 - Surveys are voluntary actions; the user is free to answer or not.
- 2) Purpose: data should only be used for the purpose stated and not for any other purposes;
 - It is stated in the User Consent and both Project Leader & WP5 Leader will monitor the data use (scientific & project purposes).

3) Consent: data should not be disclosed without the data subject’s consent;

- It is stated in the User Consent.

4) Security: collected data should be kept secure from any potential abuses;

- Anonymous data have been collected on UNITN servers, and used in aggregate way. The access to the dataset is limited to specific persons: PC, PL, RIC and WP5 Leader.

5) Disclosure: data subjects should be informed as to who is collecting their data;

- Project name, description and website are communicated. Info emails are present on the website.

6) Access: data subjects should be allowed to access their data and make corrections to any inaccurate data;

- User was allowed to go back to previous answers until submission.

7) Accountability: data subjects should have a method available to them to hold data collectors accountable for not following the above principles.

- Project contacts are communicated; users can control how data will be treated by project partners.

Fig.17

³[http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Population_pyramids,_EU-28,_1994_and_2014_\(%C2%B9\)_\(%25_of_the_total_population\)_YB15.png](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Population_pyramids,_EU-28,_1994_and_2014_(%C2%B9)_(%25_of_the_total_population)_YB15.png)

⁴<http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Documents/isced-2011-en.pdf>

⁵[http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Value_added,_2012_\(billion_EUR\)_YB15.png](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Value_added,_2012_(billion_EUR)_YB15.png)

Fig. 17

6. CONCLUSION: OPEN ISSUES

Given the participatory and incrementally-defined character of the PIE News evaluation plan and related activities, this detailed Evaluation Plan leveraged on many consensus points with project partners. On the other side, **the plan is not exhaustive** both because (i) many activities will be co-defined with partners over time when the consortium will be ready to start thinking and planning in detail every single activity step, and (ii) some evaluation activities will be changed, deleted or introduced from scratch, as result of a novel/changed project need.

The very relevant point is that at Month 5 a common platform for co-working on evaluation-related issues has been discussed and agreed with project partners, and that a more or less detailed –depending on specific items – evaluation plan structure is now ready as foundation for every further improvement.

What follows is therefore a list of evaluation **open issues that will need to be further elaborated** during the PIE News project timeframe:

- 1. User Registration Survey:** it is the first task to be co-defined starting from December 2016 in order to provide an anonymous data monitoring of registered platform users.
- 2. Self-evaluation of pilots' activities:** the specific instantiation of the IA4SI project's Self-Assessment Toolkit (SAT) needs to be done from December 2016 for a continuous self-evaluation that will involve project partners, platform users and local stakeholders.
- 3. Planning users' feedback activities for MockUps:** during the DWS2 this task will be discussed with

project partners in order to adequately planning users' feedbacks for MockUps 2 and 3.

4. Pilots' evaluation of technological solutions: 1st SW release "reputation and currency solutions" and 2nd SW release "collaborative economy and currency solutions" will need to be defined in detail with project partners – starting from the preparation of DWS3 – in order to avoid the over-involvement of users by leveraging on already planned activities and focus-groups.

5. Planning user feedback activities on 3rd and Final Releases: in-depth planning of the users' feedback on both the 3rd and the final platform releases is postponed for consortium discussion during DWS4.

6. User-Stakeholder Satisfaction Survey specific instantiations: the USSS survey template will be tailored in order to gather people satisfaction level and feedback after every grassroots' and stakeholders' involvement in project activities at the pilot level.

7. Network Dynamics Analysis: NDA needs to be further understood and planned within WP3 and WP4, then giving powerful insights for participation incentive mechanisms in WP5.

8. Final self-assessment: following the planning intermediate self-evaluation of the project dimensions with a proper instantiation of the SAT tool (see point 2 in this list), also the final assessment of the project will result.

REFERENCES

Bellini, F., Passani, A., Klitsi, M., Vanobberger, W. (2016). Exploring Impacts of Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation. Eurokleis Press, Rome. <http://www.eurokleis.com/download.html>

Land, F. (2000). "Evaluation in a Socio-Technical Context". Baskerville, R. et al. (eds.) Organizational and Social Perspectives on Information Technology. Springer, New York.

Shimanek, Anna E. (2001). "Do you Want Milk with those Cookies?: Complying with Safe Harbor Privacy Principles". Journal of Corporation Law 26 (2): 455, 462-463

ANNEXES

The four versions of the Early Users' Survey questionnaire are provided in the Lime Survey printing structure as PDF separate files:

- ▶ PIE-D5.1-Annex1_EarlyUserSurvey-ENG
- ▶ PIE-D5.1-Annex2_EarlyUserSurvey-ITA
- ▶ PIE-D5.1-Annex3_EarlyUserSurvey-DUT
- ▶ PIE-D5.1-Annex4_EarlyUserSurvey-CRO